

1. Title: Identifying Key Barriers to Implementing Smart Safety Management Systems in High-Rise Construction Projects: A Tradespeople's Perspective

2. Description: This dataset contains responses collected from 67 tradespeople working on construction projects. The data were collected to examine the barriers to implementing IoT-based smart safety management systems in construction projects.

3. File Details:

TradespeopleData – Responses from 67 tradespeople TradespeopleData – Responses from 67 tradespeople

4. Variables Description: The file contains demographic variables (Age, Gender, ExperienceYears, etc.) and survey responses (Q1 to Qn) related to organizational, infrastructure, cost, and system integration barriers. Responses are coded on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Strongly Disagree, 5 = Strongly Agree). All personal identifiers have been removed to ensure anonymity.